

Original Article

US-ISRAEL INVASION OF IRAN AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON INTERNATIONAL LAW

ThankGod Festus Lilly-Inia (Ph.D.) and Chimezie Chukwuemeka Eze (Ph.D.)

Department of Political Science, Faculty of
Social Sciences, University of Port Harcourt
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20324808>

Abstract: This study investigated the US-Israel invasion of Iran and its implications for international law. The US-Israeli military actions against Iran raise serious concerns about the legality of the use of force under international law, particularly the restrictions on self-defense and state sovereignty in the UN Charter. These actions expose weaknesses in international legal institutions, especially in enforcing compliance by powerful states. The study aimed to analyze the legality of the US-Israel military actions against Iran under international law and the United Nations Charter and evaluate the effectiveness of international legal institutions, particularly the United Nations, in addressing and regulating the conflict between the United States, Israel, and Iran. The study used the Realist Theory of International Relations developed by Hans J. Morgenthau in 1948. The study employed a qualitative research design and applied secondary sources of data, including books, academic journals, international conventions and treaties, the United Nations Charter, reports issued by international organizations, government publications, judicial decisions, legal documents, and newspapers. The study found that the legality of US-Israel military actions against Iran is widely contested under international law, as such operations raise serious concerns in relation to Article 2(4) and Article 51 of the United Nations Charter, particularly in situations where there is no clear approval from the Security Council and where self-defense arguments are broadly or controversially interpreted. The study concluded that the US-Israeli military action against Iran constitutes a profound challenge to the core tenets of international law, especially the prohibition on the use of force in the United Nations Charter. This raises critical concerns regarding the weakening of state sovereignty, the deterioration of collective security frameworks, and the increasing ambiguity in the application of the doctrine of self-defense in international relations. The study recommended strengthening diplomatic engagement and formal multilateral negotiations among the United States, Israel, and Iran, facilitated by neutral international mediators under the United Nations' oversight, to help resolve long-standing historical disputes, ease ideological tensions, and reduce strategic rivalry in the Middle East.

Keywords: U.S, Israel, Iran, Invasion, International Law

Original Article

Introduction

The modern international legal order is fundamentally structured around the regulation of state conduct and the preservation of international peace and security. Laws generally regulate behavior within society, while international law performs a similar function within the international community by establishing binding rules and principles governing relations among sovereign states and other international actors. According to Bentham (2015), international law constitutes a body of rules regulating relations between states, while contemporary legal scholarship further defines it as a system of treaties, customs, principles, and judicial decisions that collectively guide the conduct of nations and international organizations. These legal norms derive from treaties, customary international law, general principles recognized by civilized nations and decisions of international courts and tribunals. In an increasingly interconnected and interdependent world, international law plays an indispensable role in promoting cooperation, maintaining international stability, resolving disputes, and responding to transnational challenges, such as armed conflict, terrorism, nuclear proliferation, and humanitarian crises (Boulden & Weiss, 2004).

The principle of sovereign equality and the prohibition of the unilateral use of force are central to the framework of international law. These principles are firmly embedded in the Charter of the United Nations and are widely regarded as *jus cogens* norms from which no derogation is permitted. Article 2(4) of the United Nations Charter expressly prohibits states from threatening or using force against the territorial integrity or political independence of another state, whereas Article 51 recognizes only a limited exception that permits self-defense in response to an actual or imminent armed attack. Beyond lawful self-defense, the United Nations Security Council acting under Chapter VII of the Charter may only authorized the use of force. These provisions emerged from the post-1945 international order established after the Second World War's devastation and were intended to prevent aggressive wars and preserve peaceful co-existence among states. Consequently, contemporary international law imposes strict legal standards on military interventions, invasions, occupation, and the targeting of civilian infrastructure during armed conflict, with violations potentially attracting state responsibility and international accountability under international humanitarian law and international criminal law (Shaw, 2021).

The prolonged hostility between the United States and the Islamic Republic of Iran remains one of the most consequential geopolitical rivalries in contemporary international relations within this legal and political framework. The antagonism between the two states is deeply rooted in historical, ideological, political, and strategic disagreements that have evolved over several decades. Although contemporary Western narratives frequently frame the conflict around allegations concerning Iran's support for militant groups, regional destabilization and nuclear ambitions, the Iranian perspective often traces the origins of hostility to the 1953 coup d'état, orchestrated with the support of the United States and the United Kingdom against Iran's democratically elected Prime Minister, Mohammad Mossadeq. Mossadeq had nationalized Iran's oil industry and represented a nationalist movement seeking economic independence and political sovereignty. The overthrow of his government and the subsequent installation of Shah Mohammad Reza Pahlavi under a pro-Western regime altered Iran's political trajectory and generated deep anti-Western sentiments within Iranian society (Abrahamian, 2013). The United States subsequently became a principal supporter of the Shah's government through extensive military, political, and economic assistance. However, mounting dissatisfaction with authoritarian governance, perceived Western domination, and socio-economic inequalities culminated in the 1979 Iranian Revolution, which replaced the monarchy with an Islamic Republic led by Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini. The revolution fundamentally transformed Iran's foreign policy orientation and intensified tensions with the United States, which became widely perceived by the new Iranian leadership as a symbol of Western imperialism and external

Original Article

interference. The seizure of the United States Embassy in Tehran and the detention of American diplomats for 444 days marked a significant deterioration in bilateral relations and entrenched mutual hostility between the two states (Kratz, 2021).

Throughout the 1980s and subsequent decades, the relations between the United States and Iran became increasingly confrontational. During the Iran-Iraq War, the United States provided varying degrees of support to Iraq, while Iran faced sanctions, military pressure, and diplomatic isolation. Further tensions emerged following attacks linked to Iranian-backed groups, including the bombing of the United States Embassy in Beirut in 1983, which killed several American citizens. The United States has consistently accused Iran of sponsoring terrorism through organizations such as Hezbollah, Hamas, the Houthis and various Shi'a militias operating across the Middle East. The United States has designated the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC) and its Quds Force as terrorist entities accused of financing, training, and supporting armed non-state actors throughout the region (Wright, 2010). However, Iran has rejected these accusations and countered that the US military involvement in Iraq, Afghanistan, Syria, and the Gulf region has contributed significantly to the instability and violence in the Middle East.

The rivalry between the two countries has also extended into nuclear proliferation, economic sanctions, cyber warfare, and proxy conflicts. The United States and its allies have repeatedly expressed concerns regarding Iran's nuclear program, arguing that it could facilitate the development of nuclear weapons capabilities, while Iran has maintained that its nuclear activities are solely intended for peaceful civilian purposes. These tensions culminated in Iran, the United States, and other major powers signing the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) in 2015. Iran agreed to limitations on its nuclear activities in exchange for sanctions relief under the agreement. Nevertheless, the unilateral withdrawal of the United States from the agreement in 2018 reignited tensions and contributed to escalating confrontations between the two countries. The killing of Iranian General Qasem Soleimani in a drone strike by the United States in 2020 further intensified hostilities and heightened fears of direct military confrontation (Lane, 2023).

The escalation of hostilities between the United States, Israel, and Iran in 2025 and 2026 has brought these longstanding tensions into a new and highly dangerous phase with profound implications for international law and global security. Following years of covert operations, cyber-attacks, proxy warfare, and strategic confrontations, the conflict evolved into direct military engagement during the so-called "12-Day War" of June 2025, which involved extensive airstrikes on Iranian nuclear and military installations alongside retaliatory missile attacks on Gulf oil infrastructure (IISS, 2025). Although a fragile ceasefire temporarily halted active hostilities, unresolved political and security disputes soon reignited, resulting in early 2026 military operations involving the United States and Israel against Iranian targets, including strategic military installations and critical civilian infrastructure (Reuters, 2026).

Under international law, these developments raise serious and complex questions concerning the legality of the use of force, state sovereignty, self-defense, collective security, proportionality, humanitarian protection, and accountability for violations of international humanitarian law. The alleged invasion and military operations against Iran have generated intense debate regarding whether such actions satisfy the legal thresholds established under Article 51 of the United Nations Charter or constitute unlawful aggression contrary to the foundational principles of the international legal order. Additionally, the targeting of civilian infrastructure, the humanitarian consequences of military action, and the potential destabilization of the Middle East region have renewed scholarly and diplomatic attention on the adequacy of existing international legal mechanisms in regulating interstate conflict among powerful states. Against this background, the US-Israel military operations against Iran

Original Article

provide a critical case study for examining the effectiveness, limitations, and contemporary relevance of international law in the regulation of armed conflict and the maintenance of peace and security in the twenty-first century.

Statement of the problem

Although extensive international legal frameworks regulate the use of force among states, the contemporary international system continues to experience repeated military conflicts that undermine the authority and effectiveness of international law. The United Nations Charter primarily established the prohibition of aggression to discourage unilateral military actions and safeguard international peace and security. Nevertheless, to legitimize military interventions, major powers have increasingly relied on justifications such as self-defense, counterterrorism, anticipatory security measures, and the protection of national strategic interests. This trend has raised serious concerns about the weakening of fundamental principles, such as state sovereignty, territorial integrity, non-interference, and collective security, which form the bedrock of the international legal system.

The ongoing conflict between the United States, Israel, and Iran is one of the most notable contemporary examples of these legal and political tensions. The escalation of hostilities among these states, particularly military strikes directed at Iranian territory and strategic facilities, has generated debate regarding the legality of the use of force under the UN Charter. The growing tendency of states to undertake unilateral military actions without clear authorization from the UNSC has created uncertainty in the interpretation and application of Articles 2(4) and 51 of the Charter, especially concerning anticipatory self-defense, collective self-defense and counterterrorism operations. The conflict poses a serious challenge to international legal institutions charged with preserving international peace and preventing acts of interstate aggression.

Moreover, the intensification of the US-Israel-Iran confrontation has produced far-reaching humanitarian, political, economic, and security consequences both within the Middle East and globally. Attacks on strategic infrastructure, such as nuclear facilities, energy resources, communication systems, and civilian installations, have heightened concerns about regional instability, population displacement, disruptions to global energy supplies, and the possible spread of armed conflict to neighboring countries (Otubu et al., 2024). The participation of proxy militias and regional allies has further complicated the situation and increased the likelihood of wider geopolitical tensions. These circumstances have also raised critical questions regarding adherence to international humanitarian law, particularly in relation to the principles of proportionality, distinction, military necessity, and civilian protection during armed conflict.

Additionally, the conflict highlights the weaknesses of international legal enforcement mechanisms in dealing with violations committed by politically and militarily powerful states. While international law provides rules governing the conduct of war and state responsibility, political interests within international institutions, such as the United Nations Security Council, often influence the implementation and enforcement of these rules, where the veto power of major states may obstruct effective action. This has reinforced criticisms that international law is applied selectively and lacks effective enforcement in conflicts involving influential global powers and their allies. Consequently, concerns regarding the impartiality, credibility, and overall effectiveness of international law in managing modern interstate disputes and ensuring accountability for unlawful uses of force continue to emerge.

Therefore, the continued rise in tensions between the United States, Israel, and Iran constitutes an important legal and academic issue that demands careful examination. Beyond threatening regional and global peace, the conflict tests the strength and relevance of the post-1945 international legal order. This raises significant concerns about the legality of military intervention, the limits of self-defense under international law, the protection of civilian

Original Article

populations, the regulation of nuclear-related disputes, and the capacity of international institutions to maintain global peace and security.

Several scholars have examined different aspects of the US-Iran conflict and Middle Eastern tensions. Otubu et al. (2024) explored the United States-Iran conflict and its implications for the Middle East. Choudary (2024) investigated the US-Iran rivalry and its effects on peace within the Middle East, while Charles (2026) examined the 2026 US/Israel-Iran conflict and its implications for the construction industry in the Middle East and Africa. Despite these scholarly contributions, there remains limited research specifically addressing the implications of the US-Israel invasion of Iran for international law, particularly in relation to the legality of the use of force, state sovereignty, international humanitarian law, and the effectiveness of the United Nations system in responding to contemporary interstate conflicts. Therefore, this study bridges this existing knowledge gap.

Objectives of the study

The study is guided by the following objectives:

1. Analyze the legality of the US-Israel military actions against Iran under international law and the United Nations Charter.
2. The effectiveness of international legal institutions, particularly the United Nations, in addressing and regulating the conflict between the United States, Israel, and Iran is evaluated.

Literature Review

The Concept of International Law

Bentham (2016) defined international law as a collection of rules governing relations between states. According to Bentham (2016), the above definition demonstrates how far international law has evolved, as this original definition omits individuals and international organizations, two of the most dynamic and vital elements of modern international law. Furthermore, he stated that it is no longer accurate to view international law as simply a collection of rules; rather, it is a rapidly developing multifaceted system of rules and influential, though not directly binding, principles, practices, and assertions coupled with increasingly sophisticated structures and processes (Bentham, 2016). In its broadest sense, international law provides normative guidelines, methods, mechanisms, and a common conceptual language to international actors, primarily sovereign states, but also increasingly international organizations and some individuals. Gray (2018) noted that the range of subjects and actors directly concerned with international law has widened considerably, moving beyond the classical questions of war, peace, and diplomacy to include human rights, economic and trade issues, space law, and international organizations. Although international law is a legal and not an ethical one, it has been influenced mainly by ethical principles and concerns, particularly in the sphere of human rights (Gray, 2018).

Mertus (2009) conceived international law as an independent system of law that existed outside the legal orders of a particular State". It differs from domestic legal systems in several respects. For example, although the United Nations (UN) General Assembly, which consists of representatives from 190 countries, has the appearance of a legislature, it has no power to issue binding laws. Rather, its resolutions serve only as recommendations except in specific cases and for certain purposes within the UN system, such as determining the UN budget, admitting new members of the UN, and electing new judges to the ICJ (Mertus, 2009), with the involvement of the Security Council.

The concept of war

There are many definitions of what war is, but one of the most relevant is that of Hedley Bull, who founded the English school, which, in his book *The Anarchical Society: A Study of Order in World Politics*, published in 2007, gives the following definition: an organized violence carried on by political units against each other

Original Article

(Hedley, 2007). This definition has many important elements. It is important to state that war is violence organized by political units. While the idea of war is fraught with preconceptions and violence, we must be careful because we do not speak of interpersonal violence when we talk about war. Interpersonal violence is linked to crime and aggression, while war is organized violence involving organized political units fighting each other (Hedley, 2007).

Hedley adds that war has an official character, i.e., war is waged in the name of the State against another political unit. He makes a third distinction in his definition, that is, even if war is waged on behalf of that political entity, it must be waged against other political entities that are generally outside the state (Hedley, 2007). Hedley makes a fundamental distinction regarding organized violence, e.g. the fight against crime, regarding police work.

In his *Leviathan*, published in 1551, Thomas Hobbes stated that war is “the war of all against all.” Hobbes is the basis of state and war theory, and his idea is that the state is formed because anarchy reigns between individuals, and an entity is needed to regulate inter-individual relations. (Hobbes cited in Hedley, 2007). In other words, in a more sociological approach, the idea of warfare of all against all is an idea that has made it possible to develop other concepts. The state has emerged to regulate the jungle that reigned within society, and the war of all against all is an empirical impossibility because men cannot permanently fight anarchically, and individuals are reluctant to organize themselves and to fight. There may be individual aggression and selfishness that can lead to fights, but armed conflicts are something else. According to Hobbes, war is primarily a matter of human nature. Here, the idea of war against all is to be questioned because it starts from the idea that it is the selfishness of man that generates war, whereas it is the sociality of man. After all, we are forced to live in society because, to be able to wage a war, we need structures that make it possible to do so, namely an organization (Hobbes cited in Hedley, 2007).

Human organization is the fruit of a human society. This principle, stated by Hobbes, starts from the fact that man is selfish and leads to war all the time, but it is the society of man that creates war, since it takes an organization to make war, an organization that can only appear through society. Rather than being a natural and universal phenomenon, war is a social phenomenon. This reasoning does not start from the selfishness of man but from his sociality, which is the fact of living together and having to live together (Leander, 2013). To wage war requires complex organizations with bureaucratized administrations. Effective organizations that make it possible to wage war are needed, hence the unavoidable requirements for the organization of human societies to wage war.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Realist Theory of International Relations as its theoretical framework. The theory was developed by Hans J. Morgenthau in 1948 and remains one of the most influential approaches in the study of international politics and conflict. Realism explains international relations from the perspective of power struggle, state interest, survival, and competition within an anarchic international system. The theory assumes that states and political actors primarily pursue power and self-interest to secure their survival and dominance. According to Morgenthau (1948), states continuously seek ways to acquire, maintain, and expand power because the international system is characterized by rivalry, insecurity, and competition. In such an environment, states engage in power politics to protect their national interests and ensure survival.

The realist perspective assumes that human nature is inherently selfish, conflictual, and power-seeking. Realists argue that political behavior at both domestic and international levels reflects human beings’ aggressive and competitive tendencies. Richard and Sinclair (1996) contend that realism is based on historical observations that reveal persistent patterns of violent competition and struggle among individuals and states. Consequently, realism

Original Article

views conflict as inevitable because political actors constantly seek to maximize their influence and security. Within this framework, the preservation of the state becomes political leaders' highest moral obligation, and the pursuit of power becomes necessary for survival. Therefore, Morgenthau (1948) maintains that national interest defined in terms of power serves as the guiding principle of foreign policy formulation and state behavior.

Walker (1993) argues that realism does not exist as a single unified tradition but rather as a broad body of ideas characterized by different perspectives and interpretations. Timothy (1993) categorized realism into three major phases: classical, modern, and neo-realism. Classical realism emphasizes human nature as the major cause of conflict, whereas modern and neo-realism focus more on the anarchic structure of the international system and the distribution of power among states. Despite these variations, all realist perspectives assume that power and survival are central to political behavior.

Walker (1993) further distinguishes between historical and international system and the distribution of power among states. Despite these variations, all realist perspectives assume structural realism. Historical realism, associated with Niccolò Machiavelli, emphasizes the ability of political leaders to manipulate and control their external environment through strategy and force. E. H. Carr (1976) expanded this perspective by arguing that successful foreign policy must balance power with morality and diplomacy (Carr, 1976). Carr maintained that force alone cannot indefinitely sustain authority without some degree of legitimacy and political accommodation. On the other hand, structural realism is associated with Thucydides, Morgenthau, and Waltz. Thucydides explained international politics as a struggle driven by self-interest, insecurity, alliances, and power balance. Through his account of the Peloponnesian War, particularly the "Melian Dialogue," he demonstrated how stronger states often dominate weaker states in pursuit of strategic advantage. Morgenthau (1948) later reinforced this position by arguing that when survival is threatened, states often rely on force, territorial control, and political dominance in pursuit of national interest, with limited regard for morality or justice.

According to Ogonor (2007), realism is based on several major assumptions. First, no natural harmony of interests exists among states because different states pursue conflicting national objectives, which frequently lead to war and political rivalry. Second, states' capabilities determine outcomes in international politics, particularly in conflict and negotiation situations. Third, power consists not only of military strength but also of economic resources, technological advancement, population size, and strategic influence. Fourth, realism assumes that human nature is fundamentally selfish and power-oriented, thereby limiting the possibility of achieving permanent peace through moral or political reforms. Fifth, realists argue that abstract moral principles cannot always guide political actions because states prioritize survival and national interest over ethical considerations. Finally, realism emphasizes the balance of power as a mechanism for preventing the domination of weaker states by stronger powers.

The relevance of Realist Theory to this study lies in its assumption that states operate within an anarchic international system where the pursuit of power, national security, and strategic interests over other considerations. From this perspective, the actions of the United States, Israel, and Iran may be viewed as deliberate attempts to safeguard their political influence, military strength, and regional dominance rather than strict adherence to the principles of international law. The theory further explains why dominant states often undertake unilateral military actions irrespective of international legal limitations and why international institutions, such as the United Nations, frequently encounter challenges in enforcing international law effectively in disputes involving powerful states.

Materials and Methods

Original Article

The study employed a qualitative research design because of its suitability for providing a detailed examination and interpretation of the US-Israel invasion of Iran and its implications for international law. This research design facilitates a critical analysis of legal doctrines, international relations, historical developments, treaties, and scholarly arguments relevant to the subject matter. It also offers an understanding of the political and legal complexities surrounding the conflict while enabling an assessment of the effectiveness of international legal frameworks in regulating the conduct of states and the use of force in international relations.

The study used secondary sources of data. Relevant information was gathered from books, academic journals, international conventions and treaties, the United Nations Charter, reports issued by international organizations, government publications, judicial decisions, legal documents, newspapers, online scholarly databases, and other related materials concerning international law, the US-Israel-Iran conflict, and international humanitarian law.

This study adopted doctrinal and descriptive methods of data analysis. Relevant legal provisions, judicial authorities, academic literature, and documentary sources were carefully reviewed, analyzed, and interpreted in accordance with the study objectives. Emphasis was placed on examining the legality of the actions undertaken by the parties involved in the conflict, the resulting implications for international law, and the capacity of international legal institutions to maintain international peace and security.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Legality of the US-Israel Military Actions against Iran under International Law and the United Nations Charter

The legality of the US–Israel military actions against Iran must be assessed within the context of the United Nations Charter, customary international law, and established principles governing the lawful use of force in international relations. International law generally prohibits one state’s use of force against another, except in narrowly defined circumstances recognized under the UN Charter. Article 2(4) of the Charter clearly requires all member states to refrain from using force against any state’s territorial integrity or political independence. This provision is widely regarded as a cornerstone of modern international law and the foundation of the post-World War II collective security system (Shaw, 2021).

Only two lawful exceptions to this general prohibition are recognized by international law. The first is where the UNSC authorizes the use of force under Chapter VII of the Charter in response to threats to or breaches of international peace and security. The second is the inherent right of individual or collective self-defense under Article 51, which applies only where an armed attack has occurred against a state (Brownlie, 2008). In relation to the US–Israel military operations against Iran, the major legal question is whether these actions meet the strict requirements of lawful self-defense or whether they constitute an unlawful use of force in violation of Article 2(4) of the Charter.

The United States and Israel have frequently justified military actions against Iran on the grounds of self-defense, counter-terrorism, national security, and the prevention of nuclear weapons development. Proponents of this position argue that Iran’s nuclear program, ballistic missile capability, and alleged support for armed non-state actors such as Hezbollah, Hamas, and Shi’a militias constitute imminent threats to regional and international security. On this basis, some argue that anticipatory or preventive military action may be necessary to neutralize threats before they materialize into actual attacks. This reasoning is often linked to the doctrine of anticipatory self-defense, which is commonly traced to the Caroline incident of 1837, which permits self-defense only when necessity is “instant, overwhelming, leaving no choice of means, and no moment for deliberation” (Dinstein, 2017).

Original Article

Nevertheless, the legality of anticipatory self-defense remains highly contested in contemporary international law. A strict interpretation of Article 51 suggests that self-defense is permissible only after an actual armed attack has occurred. The International Court of Justice, particularly in cases such as *Nicaragua v United States* and the *Oil Platforms* case, has consistently adopted a narrow interpretation of self-defense and emphasized that any use of force must meet the conditions of necessity and proportionality (Gray, 2018). The Court has also reaffirmed that Article 2(4) establishes a strong general prohibition on the use of force that cannot be justified by speculative or hypothetical threats. Accordingly, where military operations against Iran are not based on an actual or clearly imminent armed attack, such actions may be characterized as unlawful aggression under international law.

A further legal concern is the absence of explicit authorization from the UNSC. Under Chapter VII of the UN Charter, the Security Council holds primary responsibility for maintaining international peace and security and is empowered to authorize collective military action when necessary. Military force used without the approval of the Security Council and outside the scope of lawful self-defense is generally considered inconsistent with international law (Cassese, 2005). In this context, unilateral military operations against Iran raise concerns about the weakening of the collective security system and the erosion of the UN's authority in regulating the use of force.

The legality of such military actions must also be evaluated under international humanitarian law, which governs the conduct of hostilities during armed conflict. Even where the use of force is claimed to be lawful, it must comply with the principles of distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity under the Geneva Conventions and customary international law. The principle of distinction requires parties to differentiate between military objectives and civilian persons or property, while proportionality prohibits attacks that would cause excessive civilian harm in relation to the anticipated military advantage (Roberts & Guelff, 2000). Reports of strikes affecting nuclear facilities, energy infrastructure, communication systems, and other civilian-related installations raise serious concerns about compliance with these obligations and civilians' protection.

Particular legal concerns arise in relation to attacks on nuclear facilities. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) has consistently warned that strikes on nuclear installations could result in severe humanitarian and environmental consequences that extend beyond national borders. Under Article 56 of Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions, installations containing dangerous forces, including nuclear facilities, are afforded special protection due to the catastrophic risks associated with their destruction (Henckaerts & Doswald-Beck, 2005). As such, military operations targeting the Iranian nuclear infrastructure may raise serious questions of legality under international humanitarian law, especially where they expose civilian populations to disproportionate harm.

The conflict also highlights concerns regarding the selective application of international law. It is often argued that powerful states tend to justify military interventions under expansive interpretations of self-defense and security, whereas weaker states are subjected to stricter legal scrutiny. Realist scholars contend that power politics heavily influence the enforcement of international law, particularly within the United Nations Security Council, where veto powers held by permanent members can block collective responses to violations (Morgenthau, 1948). This perceived inconsistency undermines confidence in the neutrality and effectiveness of international law in regulating states' conduct.

In addition, the military operations against Iran raise serious implications for the principle of state sovereignty, which remains a fundamental norm of international law. Sovereignty protects states' territorial integrity and political independence and prohibits external interference in their internal affairs. Therefore, repeated military strikes on Iranian territory without consent may constitute violations of sovereignty under international law. Such

Original Article

actions also risk establishing precedents that could normalize unilateral military interventions justified on broad or ambiguous security grounds, thereby weakening the international legal order's stability.

The legality of the US–Israel military actions against Iran presents a serious challenge to the contemporary international legal framework governing the use of force. While such actions may be justified by reference to self-defense or security concerns, international law imposes strict and narrowly defined conditions for lawful military action, including the existence of an armed attack, necessity, proportionality, and, where applicable, Security Council authorization. In the absence of these requirements, many scholars argue that such operations may constitute violations of the United Nations Charter and established principles of international law (Shaw, 2021; Gray, 2018).

Effectiveness of International Legal Institutions, particularly the United Nations, in Addressing and Regulating the Conflict between the United States, Israel, and Iran

The ability of international legal institutions, especially the United Nations, to manage and regulate the US–Israel–Iran conflict is constrained by institutional design flaws and the political dynamics of the international system. Under Chapter VII of the UN Charter, the United Nations was created to uphold international peace and security through collective mechanisms such as peaceful dispute settlement, sanctions, and the authorization of force. In principle, this arrangement positions the Security Council as the central authority for global security governance, empowering it to determine threats to peace and take appropriate action (UN Charter, Articles 24–39). However, in practice, its effectiveness is frequently undermined by conflicting interests among its permanent members, particularly the use of veto power, which often obstructs agreement on issues involving major powers (CFR, 2020).

The United Nations has found it difficult to function as a decisive regulatory body within the context of the US–Israel–Iran conflict due to deep divisions among member states. Although the Security Council is legally mandated to authorize collective action or impose binding measures to restore peace and security, such authority is rarely exercised in disputes involving influential states because of political stalemates (Conflict of Rights and Freedom, 2020; UN Charter Chapter VII). Consequently, during decision-making processes, reactions to military operations, counterattacks, and alleged breaches of international law tend to be inconsistent, delayed, or blocked entirely. This situation significantly weakens the capacity of the UN to ensure timely compliance with international legal obligations.

Moreover, although Article 2(4) of the UN Charter clearly prohibits the use or threat of force against any state's territorial integrity or political independence, enforcement of this rule largely depends on political considerations rather than automatic legal enforcement mechanisms. The Charter allows exceptions only in cases of self-defense or where authorization has been granted by the Security Council. However, in practice, enforcement is influenced by the strategic interests of permanent Security Council members, making consistent application of the rule difficult. This creates a persistent divide between the legal framework and its actual implementation, particularly in conflicts involving powerful states.

The International Court of Justice also plays a limited role in regulating such disputes. While it provides authoritative interpretations of international law and clarifies major principles relating to the use of force and sovereignty, its jurisdiction is based on state consent, and it lacks enforcement powers. Consequently, even when the Court issues binding judgments or advisory opinions, compliance is not assured, particularly in politically sensitive cases involving major powers (Gray, 2018).

Similarly, international humanitarian law enforcement is heavily dependent on state cooperation and the prevailing political environment within international institutions. Although violations of armed conflict laws can

Original Article

be investigated and prosecuted through international tribunals or hybrid courts, these processes are often slow, selective, and influenced by geopolitical interests. This weakens the deterrent effect of international law and reduces its capacity to effectively regulate ongoing armed conflicts (Cassese, 2005).

In the case of the US–Israel–Iran conflict, these institutional weaknesses are clearly reflected in the lack of a unified and decisive international response to escalating military actions, alleged sovereignty violations, and humanitarian concerns. The repeated inability of the Security Council to reach consensus, combined with the influence of powerful states, has further limited the enforcement strength of the United Nations system. Although the UN remains a central pillar of the international legal order, veto politics, inconsistent compliance, and weak enforcement mechanisms restrict its effectiveness in regulating conflicts involving major powers (CFR, 2020; Cassese, 2005).

The situation demonstrates that while international legal institutions provide a formal structure for regulating the use of force and maintaining global peace, their practical effectiveness is reduced in politically sensitive conflicts involving powerful states. This persistent gap between legal authority and political reality continues to undermine the credibility and enforcement capacity of international law in contemporary international relations.

Findings

1. The study found that the legality of US–Israel military actions against Iran is widely contested under international law, as such operations raise serious concerns in relation to Article 2(4) and Article 51 of the United Nations Charter, particularly in situations where there is no clear approval from the Security Council and where self-defense arguments are broadly or controversially interpreted.

2. In addition, the study found that international legal institutions, especially the United Nations, have demonstrated limited effectiveness in managing conflict due to political divisions among powerful states, the restrictive influence of veto power within the Security Council, and weak enforcement mechanisms that hinder consistent compliance with international legal obligations.

Conclusion

The US–Israeli military action against Iran constitutes a profound challenge to the core tenets of international law, especially the prohibition on the use of force in the United Nations Charter. This raises critical concerns regarding the weakening of state sovereignty, the deterioration of collective security frameworks, and the increasing ambiguity in the application of the doctrine of self-defense in international relations. It may be firmly concluded that any such use of military force, absent explicit Security Council authorization or failure to meet the strict legal threshold for legitimate self-defense, undermines the legitimacy and authority of the international legal order. Moreover, it risks establishing a troubling precedent that could normalize powerful states' unilateral military interventions, thereby destabilizing global governance's predictability and stability.

Furthermore, this situation exposes the constraints of existing international enforcement mechanisms, particularly in contexts involving influential global actors. The limited capacity of international institutions to prevent or effectively respond to such actions highlights enduring deficiencies that weaken the uniform application of international legal standards. Ultimately, the case demonstrates the urgent need for more robust enforcement frameworks, clearer and more precise rules governing the use of force, and comprehensive reforms within international institutions. Such measures are essential for preserving the effectiveness, neutrality, and authority of international law in safeguarding global peace and security.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following:

Original Article

1. There is a need to strengthen diplomatic engagement and formal multilateral negotiations among the United States, Israel, and Iran, facilitated by neutral international mediators under United Nations oversight, to help resolve long-standing historical disputes, ease ideological tensions, and reduce strategic rivalry in the Middle East.

2. Additionally, the study calls for institutional reforms within the United Nations, particularly the Security Council, to mitigate veto-driven political gridlock and enhance enforcement capacity, thereby improving the organization's ability to uphold accountability and ensure adherence to international legal norms in conflicts involving major powers.

References

- Bentham, J. (2015). *An introduction to the principles of morals and legislation*. Dover Publications. (Original work published 1789)
- Boulden, J., & Weiss, T. G. (Eds.). (2004). *Terrorism and the UN: Before and after September 11*. Indiana University Press.
- Carr, E. H. (1976). *The twenty years' crisis, 1919–1939: An introduction to the study of international relations (2nd ed.)*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cassese, A. (2005). *International law (2nd ed.)*. Oxford University Press.
- Charles, K. A. (2026). The 2026US/Israel – Iran conflict and its implications for the construction industry in the Middle East and Africa. *Journal of Security, 23 (7)*, pp. 57-76.
- Choudary, E. (2024). The US-Iran rivalry and its impact on Middle Eastern peace. *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 3 (8)*, pp. 57-76.
- Council on Foreign Relations. (2020). *The UN Security Council: Voting system and veto power*. Retrieved from <https://www.cfr.org>
- Dinstein, Y. (2017). *War, aggression and self-defense (6th ed.)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gray, C. (2018). *International law and the use of force (4th ed.)*. Oxford University Press.
- Henckaerts, J.-M., & Doswald-Beck, L. (2005). *Customary international humanitarian law (Vol. 1)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kratz, J. (2021). *The Iran hostage crisis*. National Archives. <https://prologue.blogs.archives.gov/2021/11/29/the-iran-hostage-crisis/>
- Mertus, J. A. (2009). *The United Nations and human rights: A guide for a new era (2nd ed.)*. New York: Routledge.
- Mertus, J. A. (2009). *The United Nations and human rights: A guide for a new era (2nd ed.)*. New York: Routledge.
- Morgenthau, H. (1948). *Politics among nations: The struggle for power and peace*. Alfred A. Knopf, Berlin, Germany.
- Otubu, A., Efebeh, V. E., & Sanubi, F. A. (2024). United States-Iran conflict and its security implications for the Middle East. *Malikussaleh Social & Political Reviews, 5 (1)*.

Original Article

Reuters. (2026). *The world reacts to the US seizure of Venezuela's president*.

Roberts, A., & Guelff, R. (2000). *Documents on the laws of war (3rd ed)*. Oxford University Press.

Thucydides. (1998). *History of the Peloponnesian War (Trans. R. Warner)*. Penguin Books. (Original work published ca. 431 BCE)

Walker, R. B. J. (1993). *Inside/outside: International relations as political theory*. Cambridge University Press.

Waltz, K. N. (1979). *Theory of international politics*. Addison-Wesley.